

***PROCEEDINGS OF
THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
DENTISTRY 2016 NOVI SAD***

Publisher: Stylos doo Novi Sad

**Organization of this Conference was approved by
the Scientific Council of the Dental Clinic of Vojvodina**

Editor: Dr Tatjana Puskar, associate professor

CIP classification:

CIP– Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотека Матице српске, Нови Сад

616.31(082)(048.3)

PROCEEDINGS OF
THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
DENTISTRY 2016 NOVI SAD, Novi Sad, 17th-19th May 2016. –
Novi Sad: Dental Clinic of Vojvodina, 2016. – CD-ROM; 12cm

Bibliografija uz svaki rad

ISBN 978-86-7473-598-5

a) Стоматологија-Зборници-Апстракти
COBISS.SR-ID 305389063

Message from the President of the Scientific Committee

On behalf of the Organizing and Programme Committee, I'm pleased to welcome you at the First International Scientific Conference Dentistry 2016 Novi Sad. You will be able to attend an interesting scientific programme with well known and respectable speakers from the entire world. They will present contemporary achievements in different fields of dentistry, dental engineering and technology.

We hope you'll enjoy high quality lectures and interesting presentations, followed by stimulating discussions. Apart from the scientific aspect of the conference we wish you to experience the traditional hospitality of Novi Sad and to strengthen the existing friendships and create a lot of new.

We did our best to make this scientific event a great meeting, wishing it to be both informative and enjoyable.

President of the Scientific Committee

Assist. prof. Tatjana Puškar

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ENDODONTIC RETREATMENT

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Abstract

In the case of a failed endodontic treatment, it is necessary to re-treat the root canal. Orthograde endodontic retreatment involves removing the existing filling material from the root canal with additional cleaning, disinfection and final obturation of the canal. An important step during retreatment is to completely remove the existing filling material in order to enable access to all parts of the root canal system. However, previous studies report about the inability to completely remove obturation material from the root canal walls, regardless of the techniques or instruments used for retreatment, or the type of materials removed. The aim of a study, conducted on 120 extracted teeth was to examine the cleanliness of root canal walls after retreatment. After root canal preparation the sample was divided into two groups and obturated using two different materials (gutta-percha and resilon). Depending on the technique of removing these materials, the groups were further divided in relation to the used instruments (Hedstrom, ProTaper and Twisted File) and in relation to the use of solvents (with and without chloroform). After completing the retreatment, the roots were observed on SEM after splitting them longitudinally. Photomicrographs of each third of the canal were made at 500x, and the amount of remaining filling material was evaluated by using a grading scale. Analysis of the results indicated a higher cleanliness of canal walls after the removal of gutta-percha than after resilon removal. Rotary instruments were more efficient while removing gutta-percha, and manual Hedstrom files efficiently removed resilon. The use of solvent did not significantly affect the amount of residual material on the canal walls. Reduced cleanliness after resilon removal probably is the result of adhesive bonding of this material to the canal walls, and formation of a "monoblock". It is believed that a combination of manual and mechanical methods could result in better quality of canal walls cleaning.

Introduction

Over the years, there is a tendency to increase the success rate of endodontic treatment, however, the existence of periapical lesions in root canal treated teeth is still an often seen occurrence in everyday clinical practice. In the case of a failed primary treatment, there are three therapeutic possibilities: a) orthograde, endodontic retreatment; b) surgery, retrograde

treatment; or c) tooth extraction, as a last resort [1–3]. In most cases, the treatment of choice is orthograde endodontic retreatment and, whenever possible, this method should be favored as the most conservative [4–6]. The procedure implies removing the existing coronal reconstruction and filling material from the root canal, with additional cleaning, disinfection and final obturation.

One of the most important things during establishing the correct indications for performing endodontic retreatment is the correct diagnosis of primary endodontic therapy failure, as well as a critical assessment whether repeated therapy under given clinical conditions may result in better outcomes.

An important step during re-treatment is to completely remove the existing filling material and to enable access to all parts of the canal system, since it is known that the uncleaned and poorly obturated canal spaces are the major cause of failure [7]. Therefore, root canal materials should be easily removable in case of the need for retreatment [8]. Most often, the obturation is performed with gutta-percha in combination with a conventional sealer. Recently, resilon is proposed as an alternative to gutta-percha. It is a thermoplastic, synthetic material based on polymers of polyesters, that in combination with a sealer, adhesively bonds to the dentin of the root canal walls and leads to the formation of a "monoblock" [9, 10].

The removal of the material from the root canal can be done with various manual, engine-driven and/or ultrasonic instruments [6,11–18], and in order to facilitate the procedure, various solvents or heat can be used for softening the filling material [19,20]. Recently, an increasing number of rotary nickel titanium (NiTi) instruments are introduced on the dental market, which are specially designed for the purpose of retreatment [21,22] or which are manufactured in accordance with the latest metallurgical and technological achievements [23]. However, previous studies constantly report about the inability to completely remove material from the root canal walls, regardless of the techniques or instruments used for retreatment or the type of materials removed [24-26].

Results and discussion

An in vitro research was conducted at the department of Restorative dentistry and endodontics with the aim to determine the quality of cleaning the root canal walls after endodontic retreatment. For this purpose 120 single-rooted extracted human teeth were used, with fully formed apices and with a single, completely patent root canal. The crowns were removed by a high speed handpiece at a distance of 16 mm from the root apex. Canal preparation was done by Protaper Universal (Dentsply) rotary instruments to a size # 25 (F2) apical preparation.

One group of teeth (n=60) was obturated with gutta-percha points and an epoxy resin sealer (AHplus, Dentsply), using cold lateral compaction. In the second group, the teeth were obturated in the same manner with resilon points (RealSeal, SybronEndo) in combination with a dual-cure methacrylate sealer (RealSeal, Root Canal Sealant, SybronEndo). The quality of the root canal filling was checked using digital radiographs from two directions. In relation to the instruments and techniques used during retreatment, both groups of material were divided into three sub-groups of 20 teeth. One subgroup was desobturated using manual Hedstrom instruments and the other two subgroups using engine-driven, rotary NiTi instruments: ProTaper Universal Retreatment (Dentsply) and Twisted Files (SybronEndo). For the sequence and number of used instruments the manufacturer's instructions were respected. In each sub-group, half of the samples (n = 10) were retreated by application of solvent (total 0.15 ml of chloroform), while in the second half of the samples solvent was not used. Retreatment was considered complete when there were no visible pieces of filling material during further instrumentation and irrigation, and when the last instrument for re-preparation (# 40) has reached the working length.

The quality of cleaning of root canal walls was examined using a scanning electron microscope (JEOL-JSM-6460LV, Japan). Roots were separated by longitudinal splitting, and the selected half of the root was standard prepared for observation under SEM. Photomicrographs of the central region for each third of the canal were made at a magnification of 500x. The amount of the remaining filling material was evaluated using a scale.

Analysis of the results indicated a higher cleanliness of canal walls after gutta-percha removal than after resilon removal. Rotary instruments were more efficient while removing gutta-percha, and manual Hedstrom files efficiently removed resilon. Looking at the entire sample, ProTaper instruments left large amounts of material on the root canal walls. The use of solvent during retreatment had no significant effect on the amount of residual material. The largest amount of material was found in the apical third, regardless of the type of materials removed and regardless of the instruments or solvent used during retreatment.

The results of other researchers [25,27–30] also indicated that none of the materials could be completely removed from the root canal. Reduced cleanliness after resilon removal probably is the result of adhesive bonding of this material to the canal walls, and formation of a "monoblock" [9, 25]. The fact that the use of solvent for re-treatment had no significant effect on reducing the amount of remaining material, could be explained with the formation of a thin layer of dissolved material on the canal walls [14,31], and during re-preparation this softened

material could be additionally pressed into the dentinal tubules from where it is more difficult to remove [32]. For this reason, the effect of canal medicaments may be reduced, as well as material adaptation in the obturation phase [31]. The design and type of instruments used for retreatment affects the cleanliness of the root canal walls. It is believed that a combination of manual and mechanical methods could result in better quality of cleaning the root canal walls [25,29].

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